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The Relevance Of Indigenous Knowledge In Public Safety Education In Bayelsa State Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research is aimed at discovering the relevance of indigenous knowledge in public safety education in Bayelsa State of Nigeria its specific objectives include Identifying safety techniques and materials in the study area, investigating the level of awareness the people have concerning modern safety methods and local methods; assessing difference in the learning rate exhibited by the people with local safety materials and without local safety materials, to evaluate the ease in teaching with local safety materials; and to proffer solution to the problems of effective safety education in the study area. Following two methods of data collection namely personal interview and 2 pilot safety education sessions it was discovered that the integration of indigenous knowledge into modern safety education procedure is highly inevitable. The people were better trained by this integration. Meaning that the rate of learning demonstrated by the people in the presence of local safety materials is not significantly related to the rate of learning in the absence of local materials. Based on this, the work recommended for the integration of indigenous knowledge into modern safety education programmes in the study area

Keywords: Indigenous knowledge, Safety, Safety Education, Environmental Safety, Public Safety

INTRODUCTION

Safety in common parlance, expresses a situation whereby any object, or person is harm or danger free. The free from harm or danger situation considered here may be within or around a specific territory. It could be visible or invisible, physical or social, chemical or biological, and directly or indirectly in nature. In spite of this, safety is one Social phenomenon that lacks unanimous definition of its meaning. The idea that something or some-person is safe, is understood differently by different persons of various localities, disciplines and professions all over the world. This has affected a clear description of the dimensions of safety. It has invariably unveiled safety to be existing in all aspects of nature, and human life e.g. environmental safety, health safety, occupational safety, road safety, marital safety, sex safety, domestic safety, territorial safety, public safety, etc.

Environmental Safety, being what it is, especially in its multi-dimensional facets, its importance is without over-emphasis. So it is as concerning its awareness and appropriate perception. The presence of safety in any surrounding or any human society is an impressive and needed expectation. The business of arousing interest in humans towards gaining safety knowledge and its application i.e safety education is a much needed and better experience, Safety. in modern perspective is strange to most traditional societies and so much difficulty is often experienced in an attempt to express and inculcate its whole elements in such traditional societies. According to Tamuno (2014), Virtually all human settlements (size immaterial) are traditional in origin. This makes it clear that bringing safety to lime light in any human society (especially, communities in Bayelsa State would acquire much of educational principles in implementation. Again in doing this, difficulties such as misconception by the people, let down of the educators, un-seriousness from the side of the people, etc are bound to emanate. A solution measure that is seen to have the capacity of averting all or most of the difficulties envisaged

at any safety education is the application of indigenous knowledge in the education process in our localities.

The application of indigenous knowledge in safety education is quite significant. To some, indigenous knowledge is local knowledge, and some persons call local knowledge, local techniques. Although, various persons technically perceive the term indigenous knowledge differently, the central understanding is that, indigenous knowledge is concerned with the inherent ideas, understanding and techniques of a specific people living in a specific geographical territory. as it concerns their native traditions and cultural origin (Anija-Obi 1998).

It is inherent on humans to exhibit behaviours that are innate. This is built on the fact that every human being is made up of two principal sets of components. One is the natural (i.e the innate component which could be transferred from parents to child) and the other is, the environmental component (which comes from influences posed by outside factors) based on contacts that the person makes with them (Anija-Obi, 2001 and, Ebong and Animashaun 2002). All these form his psychology, level of articulation, style of functions and behaviour in society. These factors are peculiar in each human being, and in each human society. They also make every man and human society knowledgeable, important and indispensable. Therefore, its avoidance in carrying out safety education in any local community is a plan to have negative results.

The concept of indigenous knowledge and its importance has started gaining grounds on a global perspective. The numerous works in the continent of Asia on indigenous knowledge for disaster risk reduction edited by Shaw, Uy and Baumwoll (2008) is a clear indication of the essence of applying indigenous knowledge in arousing awareness of environmental safety in local people.

Safety, as important as it is, is meaningless if humans are not brought to the fore. We must realize that the first class beneficiary to a safe environment is man. This man, is naturally knitted with culture which forms most part of his attitude, vis-a-vis communication, dressing, eating, drinking, shelter, technology, (Eli, 2023) etc. This work seeks to unveil the importance of our incorporating indigenous knowledge into our societal policies and planning, especially in our safety education and management. It is filling the gap between safety education and effective implementation of safety policies in our nation and localities. Therefore, the following are the specific objectives.

- i. To Identify traditional safety techniques and materials in the study area.
- ii. Investigate the level of awareness the people have concerning modern safety methods and local safety method
- iii. To assess difference in the learning rate shown by the people with local safety materials and without local safety materials.
- iv. To evaluate the ease in teaching with local safety materials.
- v. To proffer solution to the problems of effective environmental safety education in Bayelsa State.

The Study Area

Bayelsa State is one of the 36 states in Nigeria. It was created on the 1st of October 1996 out of the former Rivers State. It is located in the central Niger Delta region between latitude 4⁰ North and latitude 5⁰25¹ North, of the equator and between longitude 5⁰ 25¹ East and longitude 6⁰ 35¹ East of the prime meridian. With a population of 1,703,318 by the 2006 National Population Census figures, the state has a total land area of 12,000 square kilometers, approximately.

Being located in the heart of the Niger Delta, Bayelsa State geology, geomorphology, hydrology and vegetation are largely influenced by the nature and activities of the Niger-Benue River systems. As a result, the soils are alluvial in nature, the geology is typically deltaic (i.e having the formation of a delta) which is richly endowed with petroleum deposits, the climate is equatorial. its vegetation is equally equatorial which can be specifically described as being predominated by swamp forests with mixed spots of equatorial high forest trees of hard and soft woods ranging from mangrove-dominated coast to a mixture of raffia palm, oil palm and high forest trees dominating in the hinterlands. The surface hydrology is dominated by saltwater along the coast, while the hinterland is dominated by freshwater.

Fig. 1 Bayelsa State showing selected settlements
Source: Author's field work

Dimensions of safety

A deduction from the workshop material of National Registry of Environmental Professionals (NREP, 2012) titled 'Proactive Environmental Management'; safety is described as a concept without a globally unilateral definition and meaning. This is built on the fact that the whole world is made up of persons with various backgrounds and with various levels of perception. That what is safe to one person, may be danger to another person. What is extremely un-safe to another, may be extremely safe to one person. This is why classification of safety is often difficult. However, on a general note, the workshop came to a conclusion that whether belonging to a particular background or not, whether to a particular profession or not, safety is when a person or group of persons, or an environment experiences a no dangerous Condition.

Classification of safety according to types has often been difficult. This is built on the basis that, safety itself cuts across all aspects of human life and natural life as follows'

- **Environmental safety:** i.e the type of safety which considers the harmless and danger free condition of our surrounding (especially, physical surrounding).
- **Transport safety:** i.e the harmless and danger free condition surrounding modes of transport (i.e water safety, road safety, and air safety).
- **Accident safety:** is the process that leads to the prevention or minimization of accidents (whether at home or road or air or water).
- **Domestic safety:** is the harmless condition experienced in Our homes.
- **Occupational safety:** i.e the harmless conditions within the working environment.
- **Fire safety:** is the prevention of lives and property from fire in our society (NREP, 2012).

Deductions from Bariweni (2013) in his work titled 'Environmental safety management' safety is classified in five types viz; environmental safety, domestic safety, occupational safety, road safety and, fire safety. Meanwhile, the highway safety community in Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia (last modified on 22 March, 2015 in en.m.wikipedia.org/wik) describes three types of safety in terms of products and their standards as follows:

- **Normative safety:** This is when a product or design meets applicable standards and practices for design and construction, not minding the history of that product.
- **Substantive safety:** This is also objective safety, which Occurs when past and present conditions of a product is practically favourable, not minding whether standards are met.
- **Perceived safety:** This is also subjective safety i.e the Safety that involves users' level of comfort and perception of risk without Consideration of standards or safety history. A good example is traffic signals which are perceived as safe, yet under some circumstances, they can increase traffic crashes at an intersection. Another example is traffic roundabouts have a generally favourable safety record, yet often make drivers nervous.

Public Safety

Deductions from the works of Johnston, Gregory and Smith (1995) in their bid to explain, public choice theory, see anything public as having something to do with people, equity and their general survival. On a general note, public is what is free for all, can be benefited by all and. what concerns all humans in a specific geographical unit.

In an attempt to discuss public safety in relation to countries, their governance, and other units within them, Business Dictionary in www.businessdictionary.com states that public safety is any specific department of government which its main duty is to protect the populace, and keep them safe that this protection covers all aspects of people's general security (i.e the masses security) which touches their health transportation (i.e. mobility). domestics, livelihood patterns. It is discussed further that, public safety agencies in this context could be police, the military. civil defence School bodies, domestic structure such as parents, etc. Inthe context of this work. public safety means the masses protection devices, keeping them from harm whether at home or in transit or at places or anywhere: even from criminals non criminals.

Safety Education

According to Eli (1999) and Anija-Obi (2001) education has been identified as a process of creating awareness of knowledge In a person or group of persons. It is also the process by which a person or persons acquire knowledge or awareness. Education is also seen as the process of teaching and learning. The important aspect common in these definitions is the fact that education is a process.

Following the same idea of being a process, www.ask.com/business (down loaded in 2022) asserts that safety education is the process of inculcating (i.e educating) individual on various safety practices at work, at school, at home, on the road and in daily life That this will require people to have specific safety training in work environment, food safety, driver Safety, weather safety, fire safety, and self defence. An in-depth focus of this definition and explanation reveals the diversified approaches in all aspects of human life i.e involving all persons.

Indigenous Knowledge

Bisong (2007) in Eli (2007) refers indigenous knowledge to local knowledge, According to him, indigenous knowledge is the peoples own (traditional) way of reasoning and application of their thoughts to reality, both in writing, or in spoken words and physical practice. That, this traditional or local knowledge of the people could be observed in the people's methods of earning a living. making of things etc. In line with this view is the argument put forward by Fubara and Bell-Gem (1981) in their comments on a technical work-report by some Korean experts on possible flood protection measures in the Nun and Forcados Rivers area in the Niger Delta. In their argument, they opine that, while the expatriates did a good work i.e in accordance to their modern technology, their suggestions do not go in any way to solve the teething flood and erosion problems of the area, because largely. The people's native law and custom as well as the people's inherent coping patterns to disasters and harm were not put into consideration by the imported experts, Likewise, Ashton-Jones (1998) in his work on, the human ecosystems of the Niger, Delta States categorically state that. the Niger Delta people express in so many ways their God-given talents in all that they do, but the government and foreign bodies alike do not seem to recognize this is their bid to solve problems of the Niger Delta people. Therefore, the problems remain continually un-solved.

More emphasis on the significance of indigenous knowledge application to all that pertains to any locality has been stressed greatly by Owei and Eli (2003) in a research work on community response to flooding of the Kolo Creek in the Niger Delta: implications for flood management and poverty alleviation. The assent, Over the years, the people of the Niger. Delta have been inhabiting their environment which today is described by many as difficult terrain'. In this same terrain they (from old) carryout their fishing, cropping, local craft, housing and communication. That for many lasting solution to emerge in the area, an integration of their local coping methods with the modern (foreign) techniques is very necessary.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Considering the nature of this work in some suitable settlements of traditional livelihood practices was purposively selected as basic indigenous settlements cutting across the three senatorial districts. See Table 1 selected settlements for the Pilot sessions indigenous and public safety education.

S/N	SENATORIAL DISTRICT	SELECTED SETTLEMENT	NUMBER OF MALE	NUMBER OF FEMALE	OF	%
1	Bayelsa Central	1. Agudama-Epie	6	4		16.606
		2. Amassoma	6	4		16.606
2	Bayelsa East	1. Idena	6	4		16.606
		2. Soinkiri	6	4		16.606
3	Bayelsa West	1. Isampou	6	4		16.606
		2. Tungbo	6	4		16.606
	TOTAL	6	36	24		100

Pilot Programme Materials

The following were some of the materials used for the pilot safety education programme;

- i. Paddles
- ii. Canoe
- iii. Floating planks
- iv. Large floating corks
- v. Life Jackets
- vi. Machetes
- vii. Axes
- viii. Mackintosh
- ix. Decayed plantain stump
- x. Locally made sun protection hat
- xi. A long stick

Methods

Generally, data in this work were obtained by personal interviews, observations and pilot sessions.

FINDINGS

A total of 60 respondents were engaged in the field; covering the questionnaire, personal interview/observation and pilot sessions. The characteristics considered include home town (Community), sex and age. Out of the respondents 36 were males and 24 were females who were between the ages of 30 and 65 years.

The People's Awareness of Safety

Generally, it was discovered in the field that the people have a good knowledge of safety as a concept, as it concerns the home, farm, fishing port, river, community, etc. see table 5 below

Table 5: Areas of Safety Consciousness in the People

S/No	Areas of Safety Consciousness
1	Fire
2	Water
3	Sharp objects at home
4	Sharp objects in the community
5	Explosives at home and in the community
6	Felling of trees in the farm
7	Night hunting
8	Traveling by water
9	Traveling by road
10	Thunder and lightening
11	Food and drinks

Presence of Safety Laws in the Communities

It was also discovered in the field that, the local communities have regulations guiding them, in terms of safety habits. These include;

- i. Laws against the use of harmful objects in the community.
- ii. Laws against setting up of un-controlled fire at home or in the farm.
- iii. Regulations on one, first learning how to swim, before learning how to paddle canoe.
- iv. Regulations on safe handling of sharp objects Such as knife machete, spear, axe, etc
- v. Laws against the use of chemicals or very small-meshed tie nets in fishing across a creek.

Local People's Knowledge about Modern Safety

It was observed in the field that, majority of the people (i.e 95%) have no basic knowledge about modern safety see the table below.

Table 6: Local People's Knowledge about Modern Safety

S/No	Option	No. of Respondent	Percentage
1	There is basic knowledge about modern safety	3	0.5
2	There is no basic knowledge about modern safety	57	95
	Total	60%	100%

The group without basic knowledge about modern safety testified in the field that they only hear about safety on radio and other media houses. That, they have got any basic contact with the concept. It was further discovered that, sometimes, they see these things, such as life-buoys and life-jackets, but fail to understand, for absence of conscious teaching and exposure.

Evaluation of the 2 Pilot Safety Education Sessions

Respondents were engaged with 3 pilot safety education sessions, which at the end were asked to evaluate the rate of motivation and learning shown by the participants in the sessions, out of the 60 respondents, 56 declared in favour of the session with both modern safety and local safety materials, as against only 4 who responded in favour of the session with only modern safety materials. See Table 7 below.

Table 7: Evaluation of the 2 Pilot Safety Education Sessions

S/No	Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Safety education session with modern and local materials is better in motivation and learning	56	93
2	Safety education session with only modern materials is better in motivation and learning	4	7
	Total	60	100%

Suggestions for Effective Safety Education in our Local Communities

The following suggestions were gathered in the field for effective implementation of safety education in our local communities.

- i. Integration of local ideas
- ii. Integration of local people in the education process
- iii. Safety officers should also be trained with local techniques of the area concerned, for effective instruction with known examples.
- iv. Government and multi-national companies should be actively involved in financial sponsorship and direct participation.

Conclusion/Summary of findings

On a very specific note, this work has succeeded in discovering the importance of indigenous knowledge to all the modern development activities in human society (especially, in public safety education). This work has discovered the importance of indigenous knowledge to safety education in the following areas;

Recommendation/ conclusion

- i. Indigenous knowledge forms any people's basis of technological growth: and so it is in safety education.
- ii. Educating rural people is easy with indigenous knowledge approach. Bayelsa State being largely rural, cannot be easily educated in terms of safety if the procedure does not follow the people from the known to the un-known.
- iii. Indigenous knowledge as part of training programme, affirms the assertion that people learn better from the known, to the un-known.
- iv. If we must contribute meaningfully to global knowledge in terms of safety education, our ability to explore our indigenous knowledge and put into practice in line with the modern, is necessary.
- v. Indigenous knowledge, as important as it is, is largely at risk of becoming extinct. Safety is what every man and the environment as a whole need. Immortalizing its dignity is to Integrate its modern views with our indigenous knowledge

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